

Edge4Drone: Managing Landings and Takeoffs in High-Density Distribution Centers

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Abstract—Managing high-density drone landings and takeoffs in urban aerial delivery systems is a challenging, time-critical operation. To bridge existing gaps, we propose and classify eight edge-based solutions and evaluate their performance through high-density airspace simulations encompassing all flight phases. These solutions extend the previously proposed Drone Edge Management System (DREMS) with static and dynamic dronepad allocation strategies and various control levels, including more dynamic strategies. The results demonstrate that proper sequencing significantly reduces collision rates and enhances dronepad utilization. As a contribution, we underline the importance of giving complete control to DREMS during landings and takeoffs and prioritizing landings in dynamic allocations. These insights increase operational efficiency and safety under high request rates and pave the way for more robust and efficient drone delivery systems, highlighting the potential of intelligent sequencing and adaptive control mechanisms.

Index Terms—Drone Delivery Systems, High-Density Airspace, Edge Computing, Collision Avoidance, Drone Sequencing

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), or drones, has grown in popularity in recent years due to their wide application range, whether in industry, emergency services, research, or even as a hobby. Due to their versatility, drones are fit for missions in various areas, including infrastructure inspection, precision agriculture, search and rescue operations, and package delivery systems [1].

Companies are focusing their efforts on the “last mile” problem, which refers to the logistical challenge of transporting goods from the last distribution center to the final destination, usually the customer’s home [2]–[4]. The main challenge for this type of service is to ensure safe operations for people and goods while maintaining cost efficiency, security, and on-time delivery time. The emergence of the Internet of Things (IoT), mobile communications [5], and edge and fog computing [1] can significantly contribute to developing future drone traffic control strategies that enable

safe and efficient flight management, which can benefit from the distributed computing infrastructure available in this computing continuum [6].

Most studies in this area focus on collision avoidance strategies and air traffic management for a few drones, around 20 [7], [8]. For applicability in an on-demand context in a city, we need to consider a more significant number of drones and more efficient management. An important under-explored problem is the management of landing and takeoff in distribution centers since these areas naturally have high traffic density. Our previous work addresses an edge-computing architecture to handle landing and takeoff sequencing in a high-density scenario called the Drone Edge Management System (DREMS) [9]. This system comprises a drone management station with one or more dronepads and an edge manager. However, it lacks a classification on dronepads usage and sequencing control and includes only one sequencing algorithm.

Given this scenario of high drone density, this paper introduces a classification for DREMS and extends new sequencing algorithms within this classification. The main objective is to reduce the collision rate in distribution centers while ensuring the efficiency of landing and takeoff rates, *i.e.*, coping with the order arrival rate. We also identify the need for control in the distribution center besides the anti-collision algorithm. Thus, this work can serve as a foundation for future methods of organizing the airspace around a distribution center and a way to systematize such methods.

We organize the rest of this paper as follows: Section II reviews the existing literature on UAV traffic management and sequencing methods. Section III presents the proposed solutions, including the design of new algorithms. Section IV details the methodology, shows the simulation results, and discusses the findings. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by summarizing the key contributions and suggesting directions for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

The *Terminal Radar Approach Control* (TRACON) system has major elements used in aviation today, providing time separation for aircraft as they pass through gates within a circular area. This TRACON area is surrounded by a maneuvering zone called freeze horizon, which allows air traffic controllers to ensure that each aircraft has enough time to pass through the gates as scheduled.

Conceptually similar to TRACON, Sáez et al. [10] apply mixed integer linear programming to sequencing management, generating arrival routes using the presequencing and dynamic trajectory areas. These areas function similarly to the frozen horizon, enhancing airspace efficiency, but are not suited for the high density of drone deliveries. Similarly, Song and Yeo [11] propose an optimal strategy using mixed integer linear programming, introducing three arrival control and sequencing models that consider multiple holding points at different altitudes to ensure operational safety.

For electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing (eVTOL) aircraft, Kleinbekman et al. [8] employed the concept of delay absorption, where drones adjust their routes to land at a vertiport within a specified time. Their method, which includes fixed approach and departure points, uses mathematical models of flight dynamics and battery depletion in numerical simulations of up to 0.6 drones/min. A related approach by Pradeep and Wei [12], called Insertion and Local Search, combines mixed integer linear programming with time advance to manage the landing phase.

Recently, Waltz *et al.* [13] presented a self-organizing vertiport arrival system utilizing deep reinforcement learning. The system operates within a circular airspace, where each aircraft acts as an independent agent following a shared policy that enables decentralized decision-making based on local data. However, this work is limited to arrival sequencing and does not address the outgoing flow of drones, which would be relevant in a large distribution center setting.

The reviewed works highlight a gap in managing landings and takeoffs in high-density drone delivery scenarios and a need for additional comparisons between more straightforward methods in on-demand contexts. This paper addresses these issues by proposing eight new solutions using edge computing and evaluating them through simulations that cover all flight phases of the service, not just landings and takeoffs, and comparing them with literature approaches [9].

III. DREMS CLASSIFICATION AND EXTENSION

A. DREMS Architecture Overview

The Drone Edge Management System (DREMS) [9] manages drone takeoffs and landings at Drone Management Stations (DMS), which serve as hubs for various organizations. Each DMS includes dronepads and a Drone Edge Manager (DEM) that uses 5G/6G edge computing for low-latency decisions [14]. The DMS has a coverage radius of R_s , enabling it to detect incoming drones, manage the landing intent, and allocate dronepads.

B. DREMS Categorization

We introduce a new classification system (Fig. 1), dividing DREMS into two categories based on the use of dronepads: static and dynamic allocation. In the static allocation model, each dronepad operates independently with a dedicated function, either as a landing or a takeoff site. Each dronepad can serve for landings or takeoffs in the dynamic allocation model. The sequencing algorithm determines the function of each dronepad at any given time.

Another criterion for classifying DREMS is based on the control level of drone movement within the DMS: entirely drone-controlled, total DMS control, or a hybrid approach. With an entirely drone-controlled level, called the C-0 control level, the takeoff, landing, speed, destination, and detour control of all drones in the region is distributed to each drone. The DEM serves as an edge computing node to assist in managing these operations. This approach imposes significant battery and hardware requirements on each drone, as they must calculate optimal routes and avoid collisions independently.

In contrast, with total DMS control, referred to as C-2 control level, the DMS entirely guides the drones, setting their speed and destination through real-time communication. The DMS calculates all routes through the DEM to avoid collisions, and each drone follows a predetermined path.

The partial DMS control model, named C-1 control level, allows drones to receive some guidance from the DMS regarding landing or takeoff while retaining the autonomy to choose their optimal routes to the designated points and to make autonomous detours as needed.

We propose at least one approach for each category (Fig. 1). Static allocation uses two dronepads – the minimum required – with one dronepad for landing and the other for takeoff. For dynamic allocation, we examine configurations with one and two dronepads, exploring sequencing strategies that range from First-Come-First-Served (FCFS) policies to full landing priority, as well as a hybrid approach combining both. This approach allows us to establish a baseline for each control level and to assess the impact of varying the number of dronepads in dynamic allocation scenarios.

C. Static Dronepad Allocation Strategies

The static dronepad allocation strategies are identified by the prefix *Stat* followed by the number corresponding to the control level, as shown in Fig. 1. We propose three static allocation strategies: 1) Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged, 2) Stat-C1-2pads, and 3) Stat-C2-2pads.

Fig. 2a shows the relevant waypoints around the DMS in all flight phases, *i.e.*, the destinations where each drone flies. Point **D1** indicates the center of one dronepad, while point **D1'** indicates the drone approach location. Drones take off from point **D2** (the other dronepad center) and climb to point **F**, which represents the cruising altitude. Points **O** and **O'** are used to manage the drone outflow in the C-2 control level. Point **P** is located at the cruising altitude, directly above the delivery point **C**.

Fig. 1: Proposed DREMS classification.

Fig. 2: Three-dimensional representation of the delivery scenario. The cylinder represents the DMS coverage area

In the Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged approach, the drones receive no guidance from the DMS, with the intelligent component being only the SingleDrone anti-collision algorithm [15]. Thus, although there is no dedicated algorithm for managing the landing and takeoff sequence, analyzing this scenario is essential to understanding cases where control is delegated to the drone anti-collision algorithm. This situation could also arise when a drone loses connection to the centralized component, such as the DEM, leaving drones to rely solely on their local sensors to complete landing or takeoff.

In static allocation approaches, the two dronepads operate independently. Our model considers a dronepad preparation time, assuming drones must be placed and/or taken off the dronepad by an operator, or the payload should be attached to/taken from the drone. The proposed algorithms ensure that, for the landing dronepad, there are at least 5 seconds between each scheduled landing. Similarly, for the takeoff dronepad, an interval of at least 5 seconds is maintained between consecutive takeoffs. Thus, a 5-second interval appears reasonable, as the bottleneck lies in the sequencing algorithm rather than the preparation time between takeoffs and landings. Our experiments used Poisson arrival rates of up to 8 drones per minute, but this interval could theoretically support up to 12 drones per minute.

In the Stat-C1-2pads strategy, the DMS directs takeoff

drones to point **F** in Fig. 2a and landing drones between the waiting point **E** and **D1'**. In this approach, drones departing from the distribution center have the autonomy to navigate between point **F** and the exit of the DMS area, using the SingleDrone anti-collision algorithm [15], which justifies the C-1 control level.

In the Stat-C2-2pads approach, the DMS assumes complete control of the drones within its area of operation. This approach divides the altitudes for different operations to ensure noncolliding routes. Drones departing from the DMS follow a path through points **F**, **O**, and **O'** before returning to cruising altitude. Conversely, drones approaching for landing are routed from point **E** to **D1'**. This altitude-splitting method is one of the more practical ways of guaranteeing collision-free paths between the inflow and outflow of drones. Other choices could be considered, such as fixed points for departure or approach, but our objective is to analyze less structured, more straightforward approaches.

D. Dynamic Dronepad Allocation Strategies

We examined three main sequencing algorithms for the dynamic allocation strategies associated with single and dual-dronepad configurations. These included the FCFS policy, the LandingFirst policy, and a hybrid approach combining elements of both. For single-dronepad configurations, the strategies evaluated include: Dyn-C0-1pad-Unmanaged, Dyn-C1-1pad-FCFS, Dyn-C1-1pad-LandingFirst, and Dyn-C2-1pad-LandingFirst. We considered the two-dronepad configurations: Dyn-C1-2pads-LandingFirst, Dyn-C1-2pads-Hybrid, Dyn-C2-2pads-LandingFirst, and Dyn-C2-2pads-Hybrid. The two-dronepad strategies directly compare static allocation methods, providing insights into whether static or dynamic allocation better supports on-demand delivery scenarios.

Dyn-C1-1pad-FCFS is the algorithm proposed in our previous work [9]. The FCFS policy handles the scheduling of takeoffs and landings. In this approach, the drones waiting to land and those waiting to take off share a single scheduling queue. The algorithm places new drones at the end of the queue in the order they request to land or take off.

In subsequent approaches, we divide the scheduling queue into two separate queues: landings and takeoffs. The landing queue receives the highest priority, ensuring no takeoffs will occur as long as drones await to land. In all strategies with *LandingFirst* suffix, we will only authorize a drone to take off if no incoming drones are landing on the dronepad or in the landing queue. Consequently, when a drone approaches the DMS to land, the designated dronepad is exclusively reserved for landing until the procedure finishes. Additionally, there is a guaranteed interval of at least 5s between each schedule, as in the static allocation approaches.

In the Hybrid approaches, a 1-minute time window is allocated alternately to FCFS and LandingFirst policies. This alternating structure allows for a balanced time distribution between an approach that favors landings and another that benefits takeoffs while still permitting landings. During the LandingFirst time window transition to the FCFS window, the two scheduling queues are merged into one, ordered by the time each request enters the queue. Conversely, when switching back to LandingFirst, the queue is divided into separate landing and takeoff queues, again based on the entry time of each request.

In the Dyn-C1-1pad-FCFS and Dyn-C1-1pad-LandingFirst strategies, the drone authorized to land moves directly from point **E** to point **D'** in Fig. 2b under DMS control. Meanwhile, the drone authorized to take off travels from the dronepad to point **F** and then proceeds to point **P** using the SingleDrone anti-collision algorithm [15].

A similar procedure applies to the Dyn-C1-2pads-LandingFirst and Dyn-C1-2pads-Hybrid strategies, which use the dual-dronepad configuration illustrated in Fig. 2a. In these strategies, drones approaching for landing are routed by the DMS from **E** to **D1'**, and from **D2** to **F**. Beyond point **F**, the SingleDrone anti-collision algorithm governs the drone deviations.

In the Dyn-C2-2pads-LandingFirst and Dyn-C2-2pads-Hybrid strategies, which operate under control level C-2, departing drones are directed along a designated path through points **F**, **O**, and **O'** before descending to cruising altitude. In contrast, landing drones are routed from point **E** to **D1'** in the two-dronepad configuration, as shown in Fig. 2a, and from point **E** to **D'** in the Dyn-C2-1pad-LandingFirst strategy, as depicted in Fig. 2b.

It should be noted that, unlike the dynamic allocation strategies, static allocation strategies do not require Landing-First, FCFS, or Hybrid sequencing policies, as each dronepad operates independently with its own queue.

IV. SEQUENCING STRATEGIES EVALUATION

A. Research Methodology

We modified the UTSim drone simulator based on the *Unity* game engine to evaluate the strategies proposed in our scenario [16]. The simulations consider that each drone has a size of 2 m x 2 m x 0.5 m, a safety radius of 30 m, and a detection radius of 100 m, as used in the SingleDrone simulation [15]. The dronepads are 3 m x 3 m,

Fig. 3: Top view of the simulated scenario (adapted from [9]).

and in approaches using more than one dronepad, the distance between the geometric centers of each dronepad is 15 m.

The simulation scenario shown in Fig. 3 includes a square delivery area of 0.81 km² and a DMS coverage area in which DREMS operates. The DMS coverage radius is set at $R_s = 200$ m, as this distance reflects a distribution center located farther from the urban region.

There is a distance of 50 m between the delivery area and the DMS coverage area to optimize simulation time, but this value could be higher in real situations. We also set the cruise altitude to 30 m and the speed to 20 m/s to optimize the simulation time. In our scenario, SingleDrone [15] is the anti-collision algorithm in all approaches. Points **E** and **O'** are separated by a distance of 10 m in Fig. 2.

We choose the delivery points randomly within the delivery area, following a uniform distribution using the pseudo-random number generator *Xorshift 128*. The actual landing rate is the number of drones that successfully landed at the dronepad divided by the simulation time in drones/min. The collision rate measures the total number of collisions divided by the number of drones that took off.

Delivery requests arrive at DREMS following a Poisson distribution with four rates: 1, 2, 4, and 8 drones/min. Each simulation runs for 50 minutes, at which the size of the sequencing queue for Dyn-C1-1pad-FCFS stabilizes for the rates of 1 and 2 requests/min. We execute each delivery rate scenario 30 times, analyze the collision rates, actual landing rates, and takeoff scheduling queue size for each order arrival rate, and report the mean and 95% confidence interval for each measure.

B. Results and Discussion

The plot in Fig. 4 shows that the strategies with the highest collision rates are Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged and Dyn-C0-1pad-Unmanaged. This result suggests that proper sequencing of the drones is crucial, as the current state-of-the-art geometric anti-collision algorithm SingleDrone [15] alone is insufficient to prevent collisions in a crowded scenario competing for one or two dronepads. This finding is expected since drones spend significant time avoiding each other around the

Fig. 4: Collision rate for single dronepad strategies and Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged.

Fig. 6: Collision rate for dual-dronepad strategies, except for Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged.

Fig. 5: Actual landing rates for single dronepad strategies and Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged, measured in drones/min.

Fig. 7: Actual landing rates for dual-dronepad strategies, except for Stat-C0-2pads-Unmanaged, measured in drones/min.

dronepad, with only a few successfully landing, as illustrated by the actual landing rates in Fig. 5.

The takeoff and landing rates for the single dronepad strategies are limited to around 4 drones/min, as shown in Fig. 5. This limit arises from the lock of the dronepad when a drone comes for landing and has to fly from the holding point to the dronepad. For single dronepad strategies, the best approach is Dyn-C2-1pad-LandingFirst, followed by Dyn-C1-1pad-LandingFirst, which means prioritizing landings helps drone energy consumption and dronepad usage efficiency, even without analyzing the battery limits.

Dyn-C1-1pad-FCFS, as shown in Fig. 5, is unable to maintain a landing rate that matches the request rate, mainly because of the 20 s time between each schedule [9], which would support up to 3 drones/min. Even with a lower drone density, this FCFS approach has higher collision rates than other algorithms that prioritize landing, so prioritizing landing is also beneficial for safety.

Turning now to the experimental evidence on dual-dronepad configurations, we examine both static and dynamic strategies. Under the same drone density, Stat-C2-2pads presents a collision rate and a landing rate statistically similar

to that of Dyn-C2-2pads-LandingFirst, as illustrated in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. Although these similar results might suggest that both approaches yield equivalent performance, an analysis of the takeoff queue sizes, presented in Fig. 8, reveals a distinction: the static approach does not accumulate requests in the takeoff queue, resulting in reduced delay times in the delivery service.

The hybrid approaches, Dyn-C1-2pads-Hybrid and Dyn-C2-2pads-Hybrid, exhibit poorer performance compared to their respective control-level strategies, with higher collision rates, as illustrated in Fig. 6. Despite allocating half of the time to landings and the other half to takeoffs, prioritizing landings alone proves to be more effective. While the hybrid approaches slightly reduce the takeoff queue size, the reduction is minimal in comparison to their corresponding LandingFirst strategies. Furthermore, Fig. 8 reveals an oscillating effect in the queue, a result of the alternating scheduling policy.

It is interesting to compare the single dronepad strategy Dyn-C2-1pad-LandingFirst with the dual-dronepad strategy Stat-C2-2pads at 4 drones per minute, as they exhibit a similar collision rate, as shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 6. Contrary to

Fig. 8: Takeoff queue size for dual-dronepad strategies, with Poisson arrival rate of 8 drones per minute and a sliding window of length 30

the expectation that an additional dronepad would enhance safety and increase the landing rate, the collision rate remains unchanged. One possible explanation is that the shared DMS area between the two dronepads, combined with the complexity of collision-free route calculations under control level C-2, may offset any anticipated benefits.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper extends the previous Drone Edge Management System (DREMS) [9] concept with new policies and a classification to better understand the delivery scenario with high drone densities. These solutions, leveraging edge computing capabilities and evaluated through simulations, explore static and dynamic dronepad allocation strategies. The results indicate that the dronepad usage policy, control levels, and sequencing are essential factors in minimizing collision rates and optimizing dronepad utilization.

Static dronepad allocation approaches, particularly Stat-C2-2pads, demonstrate superior performance in reducing collisions and maintaining high landing rates, especially under high request rates. This approach benefits from altitude separation at the Drone Management System (DMS) entrance, which effectively partitions the entry and exit paths for drones. We also highlight the importance of prioritizing landings over takeoffs to enhance dronepad efficiency and safety. Strategies that adopt this priority manage to keep landing rates close to their respective takeoff rates, even as the request rates increase. Conversely, Unmanaged and First-Come, First-Served (FCFS) approaches struggle to cope with higher densities, resulting in higher collision rates and lower operational efficiency.

Future research must improve the anti-collision and sequencing algorithms to eliminate collisions in the simulations while maintaining acceptable efficiency, thereby making these systems viable in real high-density contexts. These results provide a direction for the future development of drone delivery systems, emphasizing the need for smart sequencing

and adaptive control mechanisms, changing the best strategy in real time to ensure safe and efficient operations.

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